

BONDED COMPOSITE DOUBLERS USED IN THE REPAIR OF CRACKED METALLIC STRUCTURE

THEODORE J. REINHART
MATERIALS ENGINEERING BRANCH
WRIGHT LABORATORY
WRIGHT PATTERSON AFB, OH, USA

ABSTRACT

Structural composites are defined, at least in the aerospace industry, as those materials that can compete with the aircraft grade structural aluminum alloys in the weight and stiffness of the resulting structural components. The fatigue sensitivity of metals and in particular the structural aluminum alloys is well characterized. But, what about the graphite (carbon) reinforced epoxy resin materials?

In this paper we will discuss some of the critical aspects of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin composites as they are applied in structural applications where dynamic loading is present. First to be covered will be the fatigue failure mechanisms now well characterized in the laboratory. Then we will cover the important topic of the repair of cracked metallic structure with composite doublers and the performance of both composites and repaired metallic structure in service.

A. OVERVIEW

Composites are heterogeneous and anisotropic materials. In their simplest form they consist of the carbon reinforcing fiber and the epoxy resin matrix. The fiber matrix interface properties are of considerable importance to the mechanical properties of the composite as are the properties of fiber and matrix. Models for damage accumulation (fatigue) that exists today are no better than approximations and empirical characterization is the rule. A well established methodology is available as the basis for elastic stress analysis and design. Failure criteria have proved to be more contentious and hence the greater reliance on empirical methods. Among the reasons for this situation is the fact that conventional fracture mechanics procedure are seldom meaningful, applied to composites. This is because their heterogeneous nature infringe the basic assumptions of fracture mechanics and because damage is usually dispersed on a microscale throughout a large volume of material rather than in the form of discrete and identifiable cracks.

Safe and reliable design with composites requires the evaluation of the effects of this dispersed microdamage on the properties and performance of the material under the intended service conditions. Thus the concepts of damage tolerance and damage mechanics have evolved. Damage mechanics is the methodology for relating the amount of damage to the reduction in levels of a property - stiffness or strength, etc.

Static vs Dynamic Performance

Fatigue of metallic (aluminum) alloy aircraft structure is the largest maintenance expense we have encountered in the operation of aircraft. In metallics fatigue usually results in cracks that when found must be fixed. In composites the usual result is an accumulation of damage and a general reduction of mechanical properties which is related among other factors to strain amplitude and number of cycles endured.

The static loading of ductile metallic alloys in the presence of stress concentrations results in small decreases in measured properties. The fatigue strength of these materials is, however, seriously degraded in the presence of stress concentrations. The axial compression fatigue resistance of metallics is superior to tension fatigue resistance. Metals tend to be more sensitive to damage under conditions where a large number of low stress cycles must be endured. Where as, high stress cycles can cause blunting/yielding at the crack tip which retards crack growth. Failure usually involves the formation and growth of a single dominant crack.

In contrast the static loading of composites in the presence of stress concentrations generally results in strength losses of about 50% of the levels obtained in the absence of the stress concentrations. Under fatigue loading, however, the composite tends to be unaffected and shows high fatigue resistance until strain levels approach static failure levels. Axial compression is the weakest point for composites due to the inability of the fibers to support load in the presence of damage. Fatigue in composites generally reduces stress concentrations around holes and notches. High strain amplitudes tend to cause rapid significant damage in composites whereas large numbers of low strain amplitude cycles cause little damage.

Composite Doublers on Metallic Structure

The interest in the use of adhesive bonded doublers for the repair and or reinforcement of metallic aircraft structural members stems from the ability of the adhesive to distribute loads more evenly and over larger areas when compared to mechanical fasteners. With adhesive bonded doublers the hot spots or high stress spots associated with holes and fasteners which require more frequent and costly inspection, are absent. The inspection of a doubler to see if it is still bonded can in most cases be simple, rapid and low cost.

The lack of stress risers in adhesive bonded structures implies and in fact has been shown to result in components having excellent fatigue resistance. The proper selection and control of materials, processes and design has also been shown to result in structures highly resistant to environmental degradation. At least two separate and distinct reasons for the use of adhesive bonded doublers can be envisioned. One is the repair of conventional metallic structure that has developed fatigue or stress corrosion cracks as a result of service usage. Another could be the purposeful design of a hybrid metallic and composite structure to produce a lightweight component such as was accomplished in the titanium boron epoxy dorsal longeron of the B-1 aircraft.

The application of bonded doublers has been shown to be feasible in the field as well as in the depot or factory environment.

Many examples of satisfactory service experience exist where adhesive bonded doublers were used to prevent growth of pre-established cracks in metallic structures as well as to cool "hot spots" and prevent fatigue cracking of metallic structure where the "hot spots" were discovered after deployment of the aircraft.

BACKGROUND

The use of bonded doublers, both metallic and composite, was demonstrated in 1970 by workers at Wright Patterson AFB, OH (References 1 & 2). This work demonstrated the feasibility of the field repair (doubler installation) of the CH/HH-3C helicopter blades. This helicopter, utilized at that time in SEA in a vital rescue role, had developed a severe problem in the form of fatigue cracks in the top portion of the main rotor spar. Numerous cracks detected in service were cause for blade replacement because spar failure during flight would be catastrophic. The shortage of spare blades threatened to ground the fleet and a quick fix had to be found. The bonded doubler concept was tested on blades statically and dynamically successfully whirl tower tested and utilized as a fix in the field until a production fix was made and new blades became available. The bonded doublers performed very well in service. Figure 1 is a drawing of the rotor tip of the CH/HH-3C helicopter. The drawing shows the location of the rivets, site of cracking and the position of the boron/epoxy doubler that successfully stopped cracks from initiating and prevented formed cracks from further growth.

Prior to start of laboratory experiments a full thermal and mechanical stress analysis was performed. Figure 2 shows the specimen that was used to validate the thermal and mechanical stress models. Figure 3 shows some of the mechanical and physical properties of the composite doubler materials. Figure 4 shows the results of the thermal stress analysis for cool down from a 250°F (120°C) cure cycle. It can be noted that in the case of the graphite epoxy doublers the resulting shear stresses probably exceed the shear strength of the laminate. Graphite epoxy was not selected due to this situation. In this specific situation increased tensile loads resulted in the aluminum spar and this was also not very desirable

Figure 5 shows two of the specimens that were used to test the effectiveness of the doublers under both open and closed (filled) hole conditions.

Figure 6 shows one of a number of rivet hole patterns that were tested in fatigue. Figure 7 shows the fatigue failure of one of the specimens tested. The bonded doubler was removed. Figures 8 and 9 illustrate composite (carbon/epoxy) and stainless steel bonded doublers.

Figure 10 is an X-ray photograph of a specimen with a boron/epoxy doubler,. Note some of the filaments are visible. Also note the cracks growing in the metal substrate. Also note two of the holes were notched and fatigue cracked prior to doubler installation.

Figure 11 shows a sample in one of the fatigue machines. The rivet holes are made visible through the doubler by the use of a phototropic coating. We were not able to resolve the small cracks with this coating.

Figure 12 displays some of the fatigue data that was generated in the laboratory.

More recently the Australian work (see references 3, 4, 5) led by researchers at the Aeronautical Research Laboratories have applied this technology successfully to the repair of metallic components which have sustained cracking as a result of fatigue or stress corrosion.

Since the laboratory data which shows that crack growth in metallic components can be slowed by orders of magnitude or even stopped completely (see reference 6) has been corroborated by service experience. This cost effective technology for the repair of metallic structure under either field or depot situations should find increasing use in both military and commercial applications.

DOUBLER MATERIAL SELECTION

Analysis of the problems involved in reducing stress concentrations around the crack tip in a metallic substructure reveal that doubler stiffness (young's modulus) is critical and that the

required doubler thickness for a given situation is inversely proportional to the modulus of the material. We have tested doublers of e-glass/epoxy, aluminum, titanium, beryllium, Lockalloy (Be 38% Al), Boron/Epoxy and Carbon /Epoxy (pitch and pan base). All have worked successfully in stopping crack growth in Al specimens when the designs were correct and the proper selection of adhesive materials and processes was made.

The criteria covering doubler material selection will involve factors, such as, allowable weight and balance changes (critical for control surfaces and helicopter blades, etc.) thickness, if on the outer mold line and airflow disturbance is a problem, geometric (shape) complexity of surface to which patch must conform, and so on.

As mentioned previously the stiffer materials make the thinnest and lightest doublers. Beryllium, Boron/Epoxy and Graphite/Epoxy materials will in general be the materials of choice for high performance applications.

Other factors including difference in CTE and required cure temperature can be very important considerations. For example when bonding carbon/epoxy doublers to a small aluminum specimen the large difference in CTE between the two materials (since the Al is unrestrained) will result in compression stresses on the doubler, tensile stresses in the Al and perhaps unacceptable high shear stresses on the adhesive or in the composite, depending upon the T from cure (stress free) temperature to the lowest operating temperature (-65°F). This stress state is exactly opposite to that desired in order to keep the crack from growing under tension load.

MATERIALS COMBINATIONS

In the repair of aluminum structural components it is always a good idea to keep corrosion problems in mind. Electrical isolation of graphite composites from the aluminum substructure has been proven to be sufficient to preclude corrosion problems in the field due to galvanic action. Problems have not been encountered with aluminum in contact with stainless steel or titanium alloys. It would be advantageous to check out each material combination for corrosion potential.

The CTE mismatch problem was mentioned earlier in the discussion. A number of workers have considered the problems involved here (see references 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7). The worst case situation is the use of a carbon/epoxy doubler on an aluminum substructure. The ΔT upon cool down to normal low temperature service -40°F is almost 400°F. We have in a number of instances failed adhesive bonds, caused interlaminar shear failure and severely distorted specimens having doublers on only one side due to the CTE mismatch between the components.

The stresses are tensile in the aluminum components, compression in the carbon/epoxy doubler, and shear in the adhesive with peel and stress concentrations controlled by the doubler geometry.

EXPERIENCE TO DATE

A number of applications of bonded doublers has resulted from the development of the technology. These include: the H-3 helicopter spar tip previously mentioned; boron epoxy doublers applied to the RAAF-C-130 wing planks starting in 1975; boron doublers applied to RAAF Aero Macehe magnesium wheels; boron/epoxy doublers applied to the RAAF Mirage 3 lower wing skins and the boron/epoxy doublers used to reduce stress levels in the USAF F-111 wing carry through structure (began in the mid 1970s). More recently USAF work in applying boron/epoxy doublers to the C-141 (numerous potential applications) has begun. All of the applications have had a good degree of success, namely that of providing extended service life to a cracked or overstressed metallic structure.

CONCLUSIONS

Adhesive bonded composite doublers when properly applied to cracked or over stressed metallic components have demonstrated the ability to provide extended service life by either reducing the stress intensity driving the crack to grow or by sharing load with the metallic structure thus reducing the chances for initiation of a fatigue crack.

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11. Specimen in Fatigue Machine
12. Fatigue Data

LIST OF REFERENCES

- 1 AFML-TR-70-241, "Adhesive Bonded Doubler for H-3 Helicopter Blade Spar"
- 2 AFML-TR-75-14, "Stresses in an Adhesive Bonded Composite to Metal Assembly"
- 3 Baker, A.A., Repair of Cracked or Defective Metallic Components with Advanced Fiber Composites - An Overview of Australian Work Composite Structure, 2, 153-181
- 4 Baker, A.A. and Jones, R (Eds) (1987) Bonded Repair of Aircraft Structures, Martinus Nijhoff, The Hague
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- 6 A. Smith, S. J. Wilkinson & W. N. Reynolds, Journal of Materials Science, 1974,9, pp 547-550
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Figure 1

Figure 2. Double Strap Specimen

PROPERTIES OF $\pm 5^\circ$
GRAPHITE EPOXY DOUBLER

F_{TPL}	= 110.0 KSI
F_{TU}	= 160.0 KSI
E_{TL}	= 30×10^6 PSI
$CTE(\alpha)$	= 1.5×10^{-6} in/in/°F
ρ	= .057 lbs/in ³

PROPERTIES OF 5°
BORON EPOXY DOUBLER

F_{PL}	= 120.3 KSI
F_{TU}	= 190.0 KSI
E_{TL}	= 30×10^6 PSI
* $CTE(\alpha)$	= 3×10^{-6} in/in/°F
ρ	= .07 lbs/in ³
ν_{LT}	≈ .35 @ 4000 u in/in
$\epsilon_{L_{u1}}$	= 6850 u in/in
$\epsilon_{L_{p1}}$	= 4010 u in/in
V_f	= .50
n.p.T	= .0053

Figure 3

THERMALLY INDUCED (COOL DOWN) STRESSES IN
DOUBLER AND ADHESIVE BOND

MATERIAL	α (IN/IN/°F)	COMPRESSIVE STRESS IN DOUBLER (PSI)	SHEAR STRESS IN ADHESIVE BOND (PSI)
STAINLESS (310)	9×10^{-6}	900	60
GRAPHITE/EPOXY	1.5×10^{-6}	113,000	2300
BORON/EPOXY	3×10^{-6}	60,000	1050
BERYLLIUM	7.2×10^{-6}	1200	100
LOCKALLOY	9×10^{-6}	1000	75

Figure 4

BONDED DOUBLER FATIGUE TEST SPECIMENS

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

